

THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATION IN MAHMUDKHOJA BEHBUDI'S PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *This article discusses the thoughts Mahmudhoja Behbudi, the representative of Jadid enlightenment, had for improving education, as well as his perspectives on science and pedagogy. At the close of the 19th and the start of the 20th centuries, Jadidism [1] made its initial appearance in the well-known Crimean city of Bokhcharoy [2]. Later, these new schools of thought spread to Kazan, the Caucasus, and Turkestan [3]. It has a distinct significance in the history of pedagogy of the Muslim peoples of Central Asia, the Caucasus, the Crimea, and the southeast of Russia. It is highly distinctive and positive from the previous teaching-learning works. The actions of the Jadid enlighteners and their perspectives on education are significant markers in the historical analysis of pedagogy [4]. The Jadidism movement has a large following in Turkestan, and Mahmudhoja Behbudi, one of its leading exponents, actively engaged in the nation's political and socioeconomic affairs, established innovative educational institutions, and continued his work in the enlightenment sector. Individuals who composed and released textbooks that could satisfy the demands of that era founded printing houses on their own dime and released multiple periodicals and newspapers to inspire Turkestan's populace [5] to actively engage in the nation's socio-economic affairs, heighten their political awareness, and organize charitable endeavors. Based on these gifts, it gave widows, low-income families, and their children both monetary and moral help. Turkestan Jadid leader Mahmudhoja Behbudi was a writer, theater artist, publisher, journalist, and theorist of the new school. He was also the first to establish Uzbek dramaturgy. He lived during one of the most challenging and complex periods in our history. Mahmudhoja Behbudi devoted his entire life and career to public education; to this end, he created textbooks and curriculum, built a network of contemporary schools, and provided students with instructional and methodological resources. He never stopped working to provide and organize publishing firms, libraries, and public education. Mahmudhoja Behbudi, the inspiration for this endeavor, was not only one of the first to build a library but also the creator of the first textbooks.*

Keywords: *new-method schools, pedagogical activity, The Jadid movement, Jadid literature, spiritual education, pedagogical activity, enlightenment, child education.*

Introduction. The father of Uzbek culture and the most prominent figure who took part in the social and political activities of his era was Mahmudhoja Behbudi, who entered the field as one of Turkestan's hopes at the start of the 20th century. On January 19, 1875 (1291 Hijri, 10 Zul Hijja), Mahmudhoja Behbudi was born into a priest's family in the village of Bakhshitepa, close to Samarkand. One of Ahmad Yassavi's descendants, his father Behbudkhoja Salihkhoja's son, hails from Turkestan; his maternal grandpa Niyoskhoja arrived in Samarkand during Amir Shahmurad's reign (1785–1880). [6] Kazi Muhammad Siddik, Mahmudhoja's uncle, raised the young man [7]. His younger uncle Adil teaches him the grammar of Arabic. He began working in the courthouse at the age of 18. Conversations between Behbudi and his contemporaries make it evident that Behbudi learned well in the madrasa of Samarkand before moving to Bukhara. Behbudi attained the highest rank of Sharia—mufti—by hard labor and perseverance, after having

fully assimilated the traditional knowledge of madrasas. Russian modernism's originator, Ismailbek Gasparali, had a significant influence on the development of young Mahmudhoja Behbudi's viewpoint [21]. This individual wrote the book "Russian Muslims" in Russian in 1881. They spoke Arabic, Persian, English, German, and French and were knowledgeable about both East and West history and culture. In his book, he argues that education and equitable engagement in the social, political, and cultural life of Russia are the only ways to protect the identity of all Muslims residing there. The first action in this direction was the founding of two new schools that will live on in history as "Usuli Savtiya" and "Usuli Jadid" [9]. Behbudi actively participated in the educational reform, which was regarded as the Jadidist movement's main tenet. In 1903, new schools were founded in the nearby villages of Halvoyi (S. Siddiqi) and Rajabamin (A. Shakuri) because of his initiative and zeal. Adib starts assembling these schools' texts. He successively wrote the works "Risolayi asbobi savod" (1904), "Risolayi jug'rofiyayi umroniy" (1905), "Risolayi jug'rofiya Rusiy" (1905), "Kitobatul atfol" (1908), and "Amaliyati Islam" (1908). Books such as "History of Islam" (1909) began to be published. The government gave Behbudi approval in 1913 to start publishing the journal "Samarkand." The Uzbek and Tajik versions of this newspaper were released twice a week. Lack of funding led to the publication's discontinuation after the 45th edition. He launched the publication of "Oyina" magazine on August 20, 1913. This weekly journal publishes announcements, poems, photographs, and articles on a variety of subjects in Uzbek in addition to analytical resources. The Caucasus, Tatarstan, Iran, Afghanistan, India, and Turkey were among the regions this publication reached. Interesting discussions and pieces about history, language and literary issues, the nation and its rights, and global issues are published in "Oyina" magazine. Behbudi believed that multilingualism was essential to the country's progress. His opinion is expressed in the article "Not two, four languages are needed" from the magazine's debut, where he states that fluency in Uzbek, Tajik, Arabic, French, and Russian is imperative. [10]. Enlightenment cannot be attained by attending a single school; one must also be aware of global and historical events, as well as the state of one's own country and everyday existence. But in order to view the people's reward as well as their fury, such a mirror was required. Behbudi's social actions were intensified by this necessity, which also brought him to the theater and the media. He now started working on a variety of projects in the publishing, media, and literary industries. His whole professional life was devoted to improving the country's educational system; to this end, he built more contemporary schools, developed curricula and textbooks, and supplied pupils with reading materials, libraries, and publishing houses. He was always planning out what needed to be done. One of the main concerns of Jadid pedagogues was the development of alphabet textbooks for schools that started using the "usuli sautiya" [11] technique. Using this approach, Mahmudhoja Behbudi wrote the first alphabet textbook in Turkestan, which was later published in Tajik as "Risolayi asbobi savod." The author practiced the alphabet for a year at the Abduqadir Shakuri school before publishing it in 1905 in Samarkand after making certain modifications. In the work's introduction, Behbudi discusses this: "Honorable schoolmasters, teachers, students, and coaches, I appeal to you and request that pupils learn reading and writing in a short amount of time by using this pamphlet of mine "Asbobi Savad" ("Literacy Guide") developed for and put through multiple tests. Masudhoja, Fakir's seven-year-old son, increased and enhanced his literacy with this manual. Using this textbook alphabet, Abdukadir, a teacher at the Usuli Jadid school in Samarkand region, tested the practicality of the age-old, intricate math approach. He used the system for three months. The teacher used the simple teaching approach we

suggested for three months to educate young men and teenagers to read and write. We kindly request that educators also utilize our "Asbobi Savad" alphabet textbook. May Allah be at your side". This alphabet has been published multiple times as a foundational textbook for Jadid schools [12]. Up to the 1920s, it was taught in schools in Bukhara and Samarkand. To educate writing, the author provides instances of husnikhat at the end of the work [21]. Kitabat ul-atfol is another significant Mahmudhoja Behbudi's textbook. The book's titles, "The Children's Book" and "The Book for Children," are two translations that some researchers have found for it. The primary goal of this study guide is to teach youth how to do business in Turkestan in various government institutions. Teachers are then directed to concentrate on helping students strengthen their written speech skills. The improvement of students' oral and written speech is still one of the objectives of teaching mother tongue and literature in secondary schools. Beautiful examples of children's letters written with varying content and purposes are provided, and in the textbook's introduction, the issue of developing students' written speech in Turkestan schools is shown. It is a continuous, complex process that spans the years from first grade to high school graduation and progresses from simple to complex. This work was compelled to be written in the absence of a manual on the subject. Regardless of the field they choose to pursue further education or employment in, recent high school graduates ought to be able to articulate their ideas coherently and elegantly without stylistic or spelling errors in written form. Mahmudhoja Behbudi seriously approached the very complex and responsible issue of developing written speech, and in his textbook, in 18 articles, he showed what students should pay attention to when writing a letter or article. Behbudi, who knows children's psychology well, uses the method of writing letters, which is extremely convenient for students and arouses interest in the development of written speech. Because of that, young children use letter writing as a more fun way to write letters to their parents and friends. Because young children are very interested in writing letters to their parents and friends. The author of the textbook provides valuable guidance to teachers on letter writing etiquette, rules, symbols, and emotional signs (punctuation). Mahmudhoja Behbudi, like other contemporary thinkers, paid special attention to the issue of teaching geography. The full title of his textbook "General Geography of Muntakhabi" on this subject is called "Book of Muntakhabi Geography General and Model Geography". As mentioned in the introduction to the work, Behbudi used about 30 atlases, maps, dictionaries, and books in Turkish, Arabic, Persian, and Russian languages to create this work on geography. In this work, the author presents the vocabulary and meaning of the words "geography," "natural geography," "Umran geography," "economic geography," and "political geography", "geography and mathematics" on this subject; provides more science-based information. The history of geography, "kurrayi musattaha," the history of the creation of geographical maps of the globe, and the importance of geography are discussed in detail. In the process of distributing Behbudi's textbook, Shamsiddin Sami's "Qamus ul-Olam" and Ismail Gasprinsky's "Ulamosi of Turkistan" were used more. The author mentions the works of Muslim scientists, especially from Turkestan, who created dozens of works on the science of geography. At the same time, special attention is paid to the services of European scientists in the development of science. The important educational and methodological aspects of Behbudi's textbook are that the author did not ignore the level of knowledge of the population of Turkestan in geography and related subjects when creating the textbook. Although the geographical processes described in the textbook seem very simple and primitive from today's point of view, it was a very correct method from the methodological point of view because the level of knowledge of our people in the field

of geography at the beginning of the last century showed it. Mahmudhoja Behbudi's son Munavvarkari Abdurashidkhan supported and helped in the work of expanding the network of modern schools in the Behbudi method, training modern teachers; indeed, Behbudi wrote in his articles about Munavvarkari's work in Tashkent and the existence of his school, and he writes about the possibility of sending students to his school for three or four months to study at his school. At the beginning of the 20th century, like radical changes in life, new genres began to successfully enter Uzbek literature and art. The ancients well understood that the factor of society's development, first of all, depends on education and enlightenment. Behbudi created the first national drama among Central Asian artists: "Padarkush." Until this work, no work was created in this field in Turkish or Persian, and it was a great event for Behbudi's era. This work created by the author is the first universally recognized example of Uzbek artist. Experts evaluate "Padarkush" as a work that started a new Uzbek literature both in terms of genre and content. This 3-act, 4-scene drama by Behbudi, titled "National Tragedy," is very compact in terms of volume, but it tells the story of ignorance, how an uneducated child goes into bad ways and kills his father. This work, described by the author as a "national tragedy," refused to do this good work, despite having the ability to educate and enlighten the children of the nation in all aspects and to elevate the society to which he belongs. It was a prophecy about the fate of people. In some parts of the drama, rather than showing the idea of the work based on sharp conflicts, clashes, and character struggles, it is possible to show that the development of the country through education and the refusal of Turkestan youth to learn will lead to bad consequences, or emphasize the didactic image. Serious problems such as strengthening education and training, saving the people from age-old ignorance and backwardness, social relations such as crime and punishment, and obligations and responsibilities are clearly and impressively expressed in the dramaturgy. For the first time in the work, serious life problems are openly shown to Turkestan people in their own language, through typical images and typical characters. Ignorance and straying from the right path bring unhappiness and real trouble to the family, so the action on the stage amazes the viewer and covers his whole body. Any viewer who correctly perceives the events on the stage will cry when he sees what is the main tragedy of Turkestan; he will understand the need to bring the country's youth to a new life through education. In the opinion of Vadud Mahmud, who gained great fame among Turkestan jadids and played a major role in the formation of the school of literary criticism, "Mahmud Khoja's horse is a horse that occupies a worthy place in the history of the people of Turkestan as a decorative classic." As the leader of the Jadid movement in Turkestan, Mahmudhoja Behbudi took an active part in practical work useful for the people: he participated in the establishment of Jadid schools. His "Behbudiya Library" is of special importance among the good works started for the development of the Behbudiya nation. As noted by historian Begali Kasimov, Behbudi was the publisher of the first local newspaper and national magazine in Samarkand, the author of the first national dramaturgy, and the "first theoretician and practitioner" of Ustuli Jadid schools in Turkestan. Textbook, Behbudi was one of the first to establish a library. The main purpose of this library is to support the aspirations of local Muslim youth and madrasah students towards modern sciences. Along with this activity, Mahmudhoja Behbudi was also engaged in publishing. For the first time, his "Nashriyoti Behbudiya" publishing house translated his maps of Turkestan, Bukhara, Khiva, textbooks, drama "Padarkush," and Fitrat's "Indian Tourist" [12] into Russian. In his time, Behbudi was the only teacher who wrote, published, and distributed textbooks for the schools he opened under his leadership. "Behbudiya Library" and "Behbudiya Publishing House" served the

people together. The publishing house and the library were intellectual centers that illuminated Behbudi's modern image.

Discussion. Mahmudhoja Behbudi, who left a name in history as the head of the caravan of Jadids, was of great importance in his activities at the beginning of the 20th century [13]. Mahmudhoja Behbudi deeply studied religious and secular sciences; his articles and works are of social importance even today. In particular, the incomparable contribution to the development of spiritual culture, which is the core of culture, has not lost its relevance even today. It can be said that the collectivism typical of Eastern thinkers is also reflected in Behbudi's work. This is confirmed by the activity of our patriotic intellectuals in every field of science. In particular, we can cite his articles on science, ethics, religion, art, and politics, the drama "Padarkush," and textbooks such as "Kitab-ul-atvol" written for schoolchildren. The ancient enlighteners considered knowledge to be the only way to save the people from ignorance, awaken their thinking, and achieve progress. That is, "If you look at other nations, you will see that they have regular schools, and secular sciences are studied in the first place in addition to religious sciences. Because secular sciences are necessary to stay in the world. A nation deprived of modern science and technology suffers from other nations", [15] says Mahmudhoja Behbudi. M. Behbudi's article "Address to the Honorable Youth" mentions the importance of the development of education. Knowledge is the main intellectual source, and today, when education is valued as a source of national prosperity, the views of the thinker are extremely relevant because education enables the development of a person's creative abilities, deepens his participation in society, and contributes effectively to the development of society. It is very important that special attention is paid to the issues of education and upbringing. It is not difficult to reach. The enlightened scholar has repeatedly emphasized the need to educate young people abroad and equip them with new ideas and knowledge. Let the children be sent to government schools instead of weddings and marakas, and for this reason, the students should be sent to Mecca, Medina, Egypt, Istanbul, and Russia's pharmaceutical industries, and efforts should be made to educate religious, secular, and modern people. We have few teachers in Turkestan, so it is necessary to send a child to the Caucasus, Crimea, Orunburg, and Kazan to learn the method of education with the money spent on weddings and maraka. In modern education in Uzbekistan, great attention is paid to the education of young people abroad. Students study in the world's leading higher education institutions on the basis of special programs. We can see that these ideas of our ancestors are still relevant today. In particular, the issue of language was always in the focus of Behbudi's attention, and he considered it necessary to know several languages for the development of the nation. He urged the youth to learn the language and gain knowledge. On August 20, 1913, the first issue of "Oyina" magazine published an article entitled "Not two, but four languages are needed." [17]. In the drama "Padarkush," Behbudi described the pitiful harm that ignorance and lack of enlightenment bring to the life of the nation, to the representatives of every nation. It is not for nothing that the work is called "Padarkush or the work of an uneducated child." Our contemporaries noted that the work "Padarkush" was written under the influence of a real incident that happened in life. No matter how true or how contradictory this idea is, it does not lose its relevance today. In the drama "Padarkush", Behbudi tried to warn both them and Uzbek society of the beginning of the 20th century by showing that not only the father drowned in the swamp of ignorance, but also the lives of his children can end in tragedy. The idea of enlightenment, which reveals the essence of modernism, determines the great social and educational importance of the work and shows that it is dedicated to the most important and urgent

topic of that time. Serious problems such as strengthening education and training, protecting people from age-old ignorance and backwardness, social relations such as crime and punishment, and obligations and responsibilities are presented in the work in a simple and impressive way. Behbudi goes to Bayramali, Ashgabat, Krasnovodsk, Kislovodsk, Pyatigorsk, Zheleznovodsk, Rostov, Odessa, Jerusalem, Beirut, Jaffa, Khalil al-Rahman, Port Said, and Sham. Based on this trip, "Oyina" magazine publishes many articles on culture, enlightenment, technical development, and the development of our country. Analyzing the daily lifestyle of various events, from weddings to national games, in his article titled "Our actions are our wishes," he calls on the people to open their eyes and look at the work and life of the surrounding nations. The fact that the local population cannot give up old traditions and old views that are an obstacle to development, that they are backward, that Muslims also want development, prosperity, enlightenment, strive for innovation, and need to learn new things, now they see themselves. Our past is great. Put forward the ideas that it is time to draw the right conclusions from our mistakes, to look for ways to develop, to be respected by others, to communicate with them as equals, and to think about what we should do, to protect the interests of Muslims. He calls on the people to abandon extravagance and direct the funds spent on them to the education of children in state educational institutions in order to train national personnel in all sectors of the national economy. In the article "Diseases that are gnawing at us", he says: "Wedding and maraka, which lead us to crisis and danger, to hell, are a cure for the enemy" [15]. Behbudi has published many articles on the issue of religion and the book "Appeals to Respectable Young People." Behbudi belonged to one of the enlightened dynasties in Samarkand. His father was a descendant of Behbudhoja Salihhoja Ahmed Yassavi; his grandfather and father were qari and imam-khatib, and his uncle Mufti Mullah Adil Muhammad Siddiq was a mufti. Behbudi, who has acquired religious knowledge since childhood, later works as a mirza under his uncle, gets acquainted with the work of a judge, and learns the necessary knowledge for mufti. "At that time, there were countless courtrooms, judges, and muftis who served in every city and district of Former Turkestan. However, a perfect person like Behbudi is not only an excellent scholar of religious science but also of modern sciences. In terms of his political and social activity and breadth of knowledge, there is probably no one equal to him among Turkestan contemporaries of that time" [15]. Due to his tireless work on fiqh books, he quickly received the title of mufti and served as mufti in Jomboy until the end of his life. There are many examples of how he usually went to Jomboy once a week on Saturdays and provided a positive solution to controversial issues with the judges, and it is emphasized that Behbudi mufti and Imam Khatib are also aware of science and knowledge, modern sciences, and the past.

Results. The famous Uzbek pedagogue and writer Mahmudhoja Behbudi expressed his views on mutual cooperation, humanitarianism, and the national environment in different years. Behbudi's important pedagogical views are aimed at educating many students in the spirit of self-development and humanitarianism. During his pedagogical activity, Mahmudhoja Behbudi paid great attention to educational issues. He was one of the persons who included and followed the main values of student education in the conditions of his time and society. The leader of Turkestan Jadids, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, connected the ways of opening the eyes of the nation and liberating it from the age-old yoke of slavery with educating the people's spiritual and moral aspects. First of all, the activities to establish new modern schools that perfectly teach religious and worldly sciences, to raise the children who are the future of the nation to the level of perfection, and to change public consciousness by establishing newspapers and magazines, organizing theater

groups, and exposing some of the vices of people were aimed to enrich its culture. In the pedagogical activity of Mahmudhoja Behbudi, the field of education is one of the important issues of developing Uzbek national education and instilling the spirit of humanity into the minds of students. His ideas and influence still exist in the educational system of Uzbekistan.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it should be noted that Mahmudhoja Behbudi is one of the representatives of modern enlighteners who sought to unite modernists in Central Asia. Mahmudhoja Behbudi was one of the admirers of Ismailbey Gaspirali, who was in regular contact with open-minded, enlightened Muslims in Tsarist Russia. [18] Mahmudhoja Behbudi's enlightenment and optimistic view of the future managed to follow the modern enlighteners who left behind him; he asked Muslims to look at the world with open eyes, without giving up historical Islamic-Eastern teachings and Russian and European intellectuals. [19] Mahmudhoja Behbudi was one of the first to promote the new art of theater and cinema in order to make the people enlightened and intelligent, as well as a simple and convenient way to achieve the goal [20].

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